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SYMBOLIC REPRESENTATIONS OF RELIGIOUSLY MARKED ALLUSIONS IN THE LITERARY TEXT

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ANNOTATION

The article imparts the information on religiously marked allusions, their symbolic representations in English literary texts and analysis from the perspectives of cognitive linguistics. Among its other aspects, the research places particular emphasis on symbolic functions outperformed by allusions and in order to reveal the symbolic significance generated in the semantic layer of religiously marked allusions, the methods of conceptual analysis and conceptual blending were applied. The results of the analysis show that religiously marked allusions activate religious knowledge structures, implicitly symbolize abstract phenomena, convey conceptual meaning and express the author's individual world picture.

Key words: allusion, religiously marked allusion, symbol, conceptual integration, implicit message, precedent text, recipient text

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DINIY MARKERLANGAN ALLYUZIYALARNING BADIY MATNDA SIMVOLIK TASVIRLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada diniy markerlangan allyuziyalar, ularning ingliz badiiy matnlaridagi ramziy ko'rinishlari haqida ma'lumot hamda ushbu til birliklarining kognitiv tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan tahlili berilgan. Tadqiqotda allyuziyalarning aynan simvolik funksiyasiga katta e'tibor qaratilgan bo'lib, diniy markerlangan allyuziyalarning semantik qatlamida hosil bo'lgan ramziy ma'noni ochib berish uchun konseptual tahlil va konseptual blending tahlil usullari qo'llanilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, diniy markerlangan allyuziyalar diniy bilim tuzilmalarini faollashtiradi, mavhum hodisalarni simvol sifatida aks ettiradi, konseptual ma'noni bildiradi va muallifning individual dunyo qarashini ifodalaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: allyuziya, diniy markerlangan allyuziya, simvol, konseptual integratsiya, yashirin ma'lumot, pretsedent matn, retsipient matn

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muhayyo.fayzullayeva.93@mail.ru**СИМВОЛИЧЕСКИЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЯ РЕЛИГИОЗНО МАРКИРОВАННЫХ
АЛЛЮЗИЙ В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОМ ТЕКСТЕ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В статье представлена информация о религиозно маркированных аллюзиях, их символической репрезентации в англоязычных художественных текстах и анализе с позиций когнитивной лингвистики. Среди других аспектов в исследовании особое внимание уделяется символическим функциям аллюзий и для выявления символической значимости, генерируемой в семантическом слое религиозно маркированных аллюзий, были применены методы концептуального анализа и концептуальной интеграции. Результаты анализа показывают, что религиозно маркированные аллюзии активизируют структуры религиозного знания, имплицитно символизируют абстрактные явления, передают концептуальный смысл и выражают индивидуально-авторскую картину мира.

Ключевые слова: аллюзия, религиозно маркированная аллюзия, символ, концептуальная интеграция, имплицитное сообщение, прецедентный текст, реципиентный текст.

Introduction. Allusion is delineated as a multifaceted linguistic phenomenon and thus is interpreted quite broadly, but largely known as a stylistic tool that bears a deliberate action of an author to implicitly refer to a preceding phenomenon (person, object, event) (Ashurova D.Yu., 2005; 8). However, with the development of the sciences of anthropocentric paradigm, many stylistic phenomena were reconsidered. Being among those stylistic devices, allusion is now on the spotlight of such sciences as cognitive, pragmatic and cultural linguistics, thus is being scrutinized from different perspectives. The study over allusions can be found in the works of Galperin (1981), Fateeva (2000), Kusmina (2004), Gornakova (2010), Vasileva (2011), Ashurova (2012, 2016), Djusupov (2006, 2011), Arnold (2014), Galieva (2018) and in many more scholarly works of other linguists. Allusion is defined as a common and frequently used intertextual marker, since it establishes a bond between the precedent and recipient literary texts (Fateeva, 1998, 2000; Kusmina, 2004; Piego-Gro, 2008; Arnold, 2014). It is of significance to note that allusion partakes in the formation of author's either trite or genuine image/style of writing, and immensely assists in the revelation of the author's modality inherit in the literary text. In other words, allusion explicates the personality of the author and helps to decode his/her individual conceptual world picture (Tukhareli, 1984; Dronova, 2006). Important of all, allusion embraces conceptual information, correct interpretation of which explicates deep semantic layer of the text in its relation to the preceding source [Kristeva, 1980; Fateeva, 2000; Molchanova, 2007; Piego-Gro, 2008; Dusabaeva, 2009; Ashurova, Galieva, 2016, 2018] (cited in Galieva M.R., 2018; 158). Allusion is characterized by polyfunctionality, for it fulfills stylistic, pragmatic, cognitive and socio-cultural functions. Stylistic functions of allusions are aimed to express imagery, emotiveness, evaluation and expressiveness. Pragmatic functions are targeted at producing a certain emotional or intellectual impact on the reader. Cognitive functions deal with the representation of knowledge structures and conceptual picture of world. Socio-cultural functions entail the expression of cultural and aesthetic values and national specifics of linguistic units and literary texts as a whole. The aim of our research is to dwell upon one of the essential functions - symbolic representations of allusions, in particular its religious type, in the literary text. Religiously marked allusion itself (henceforth RA), the object of our investigation, is denoted as an indirect reference to a religious source and as an extended transmitter of the knowledge about mythological, religious heroes, objects and events to those actions, facts and personages addressed to in the text recipient.

Main part. As has been remarked above, of huge significance is to discuss symbolism created by RA in the literary text. It is worthy of note that the two stylistic devices, symbol and allusion, have

much in common, as the structure and set of functions outperformed by symbols interweave with those of allusions: a) both represent knowledge structures; b) both function in the literary text highlighting the most salient features of an object or phenomena; c) both symbol and allusion detected in the literary text should be conceptualized and interpreted; d) both can be of universally known and nationally specific. The commonality between allusion and symbol is also manifested by the fact that in the literary text allusion can acquire a symbolic meaning: it can represent a symbol, it can be regarded as a symbol. In other words, allusions symbolize abstract phenomena in the literary text, and as a result, symbolic perception of the sequences of events leads to the decipherment of the hidden conceptual information conveyed via allusions.

As a method of analyzing symbolic significance of RA and interpreting conceptual information embodied in the semantic construct of RA, cognitive mechanisms of conceptual analysis and conceptual blending (integration) can effectively be implemented. The method of conceptual analysis is intended to study functional and conceptual significance of allusions, to explicate the symbolic meaning of this stylistic device and also to decode the conceptual information of the text and author's individual world picture. Conceptual integration theory was first pushed forward by G. Fauconnier and M. Turner in 2002. They asserted that conceptual integration implies a mental activity in which "new meanings" are made "out of old" (Fauconnier, Turner, 2002; 18). To attain this, a set of deliberate actions are to be performed: ".. setting up mental spaces, matching across spaces, projecting selectively to a blend, locating shared structures, projecting backwards to inputs, recruiting new structure to the inputs or the blend, and running various operations in the blend" (Fauconnier, Turner, 2002; 18). In other words, conceptual blending entails generating mental spaces and interaction between input domains and creating new conceptual meaning. So those indispensable mental spaces partaking in the process of integration are conceptual domains, generic space and the blend itself. In the process of conceptual integration, generic space incorporates and conjoins the two domains by deducing the commonalities between them, this, in its turn, results in the emergence of the blend, a new conceptual structure. More specifically, the source domain provides background knowledge, which is synthesized and transferred to describe the target domain. It is of expedient importance to remark that the blended space originated from the joint domains bears the most salient elements of both inputs, howbeit during the running of the integration process it obtains novel and unique assets too.

All in all, allusions representing and symbolizing a particular object, personage or event anew in the text recipient are regarded as the linguistic units that activate the mechanism of conceptual integration: they accumulate the knowledge structures belonging to the precedent text and represent the old information with either totally new or additional shades in the recipient text.

According to Galperin, literary texts bear factual, subtextual and conceptual information (Galperin, 2007). So, first of all, the successful implementation of conceptual blending requires the exposition of factual, subtextual and conceptual information embedded in the literary text. To attain the research aim, the following steps should be taken in gradual succession: 1. Factual information which exists on the surface layer of the text should be divulged. To attain this, the plot of the text, the main sequences of events should be apprehended; 2. Subtextual information which is implicitly delivered via different language means (particularly such stylistic devices as cognitive metaphor and allusion) should be detected and the essence formed by them is to be explicated; 3. Conceptual information created via symbolism should be revealed. In this respect, the method of conceptual integration can be addressed to and the symbolic meaning of allusion can be revealed.

To justify our claim we intend to present the analysis of the religious allusion represented in the short story "Gift of the Magi" by O' Henry.

Interpretation of the factual information

"Gift of the Magi" by O' Henry is a famous short story most profoundly known as the hymn of unconditional love. Mr. and Mrs. Dillinghams live not in favorable conditions with lower family budget. How pure and unconditional their love is, can be witnessed in the end of the story when they at last hand in their Christmas gifts to each other: Della's present is just the thing that she longed for so long - *"Beautiful combs, with jewels, perfect for her beautiful hair"*, but alas they turn out to be

useless now as her hair is cut off and sold to buy *"Something nearly good enough. Something almost worth the honor of belonging to Jim"*. Meanwhile Jim is also deprived from the delight of possessing a gold chain presented to him to use with his gold watch since it is sold to make his beloved happy. So the most valuable and precious things belonging to the Dellingham Youngs, with which they used to feel extreme pride, Jim's heirloom, a gold watch and Della's hair, like a brown cascade are sacrificed for the sake of love. Therefore, O' Henry confesses and claims that Jim and Della are the true magi.

Interpretation of the subtextual information

The main concept around which the sequences of events are constructed is "gift", as it stands out as the recurrent element in the story forming the main ideology pushed forward by the author: the art of giving a gift. So the "gift" in the story can be regarded as a symbol of a "spiritual" offer rather than a "material" object. Further denotative meanings of the concept will be outlined.

1. Dictionary meaning of the term "gift":

In the dictionary of Britannica, gift is defined as *"something that is given to another person or to a group or organization"*. According to the conception made in the dictionary of Merriam Webster gift can largely be apprehended as *"something voluntarily transferred by one person to another without compensation"*. Roget's Thesaurus singles out the following synonymous line of the word "gift": *allowance, award, benefit, bonus, contribution, donation, endowment, favor, grant, legacy, offering, present, benefaction, bequest, bestowal, charity, courtesy*.

All in all, denotative meaning of the word "gift" signifies a present voluntarily offered to someone as a sign of affection, recognition and appreciation. To reveal additional connotative meaning attached to the primary meaning of the word is of paramount importance in the complete explication of the concept. As a matter of fact, the lexeme "gift" is a religiously marked allusion as it indirectly refers to the biblical event when Christ, being a newborn, is visited and offered presents by the three wise men (Matthew, 2:1–12). Besides that, the lexeme "gift" can be encountered in several other biblical verses too.

2. Biblical origin of the term "gift":

The analysis of the biblical verses instigates that gift is perceived as something unbelievably valuable presented by God:

"For the wages of sin is death, but the free gift of God is eternal life in Christ Jesus our Lord" (Romans 6:23).

"If you then, who are evil, know how to give good gifts to your children, how much more will your Father who is in heaven give good things to those who ask him!" (Matthew 7:11)

"If any of you lacks wisdom, let him ask God, who gives generously to all without reproach, and it will be given him" (James 1:5).

"Also that everyone should eat and drink and take pleasure in all his toil—this is God's gift to man" (Ecclesiastes 3:13).

"Thanks be to God for his inexpressible gift!" (2 Corinthians 9:15)

"Every good and perfect gift is from above, coming down from the Father of the heavenly lights, who does not change like shifting shadows" (James 1:17)

"You will be enriched in every way so that you can be generous on every occasion, and through us your generosity will result in thanksgiving to God" (Corinthians 9:12)

Overall, biblical verses testify that gift is believed to be a heavenly award given to men by God. The gift shared by God is unique for a) it has no equation at all (*eternal life*), b) God's gift is so tremendous that no any living creature can bear the same (*how much more will your Father who is in heaven give good things to those who ask him*), c) God is the most generous to give what is asked (*gives generously to all without reproach*).

Interpretation of the conceptual information

The conceptual and symbolic significance that the RM "Gift of the Magi" obtains in the story is exposed via the implementation of conceptual integration mechanism in our research.

As it can be seen, the RA “Gift” appears to be the main concept of the story. The conceptual analysis of the story and conceptual blending analysis reveal the cognitive structure of this concept including such constituents as “sacrifice” and “wisdom”. So in the author’s reflection true love means Wisdom (*like the wisdom of the Magi*) and Sacrifice (*like young men’s sacrifice of their precious things*).

Conclusion. To sum up, the following inferences were deduced from the research:

- Allusion as an intertextual marker fulfills various stylistic, pragmatic, socio-cultural and symbolic functions in the literary text;
- One of the most essential functions of allusions is to represent symbolic meanings i.e. symbolic characterization of particular phenomena;
- The conceptual analysis of the whole story in general and allusion in particular reveals the symbolic meaning of the RA and at the same time the author's evaluation of the described event. In other words, the RA in the literary text is aimed a) to represent religious knowledge structures, b) to express its symbolic meaning; c) to construct a concept of the whole story; d) to explicate the author's modality and his individual world picture.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

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